

Reactions of Cu(II), Ni(II), Pd(II), with Hydroxy Ketoximes

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Ortho-hydroxy acetophenone oxime and its 5-methyl derivative react with Cu(II), Ni(II) and Pd(II), giving coloured, insoluble complexes. The composition of these metal complexes has been determined to be 1 : 2 (metal : ligand). The structure of these complexes has been determined by studying their infra-red spectra. In the complexes, the absorption band of the free phenolic group is absent while the bands due to =N-OH of the oxime group are intact, showing thereby that the phenolic hydrogen is replaced by the metal during complex formation. The stretching frequency of C=N is also lowered in the complexes, thus pointing to the coordination of the metal to the nitrogen of the oxime group. The low frequency of OH of the oxime group indicates strong intramolecular hydrogen bonding in the complexes.

Elementary studies on the interaction of Cu(II) with salicylaldoxime¹, of number of metal ions with orthohydroxy acetophenone oxime² and of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Pd(II) with 2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone oxime³ are reported in the literature. The present investigations are aimed at determining the structure of these complexes.

EXPERIMENTAL

The solutions of ortho-hydroxy acetophenone oxime and 2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone oxime were prepared in 50% ethanol, stock solutions of copper sulphate, nickel sulphate and palladium chloride were prepared in double-distilled water and standardised gravimetrically.

The complexes were prepared and isolated as reported in the literature^{2,3}.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Ortho-hydroxy acetophenone oxime and its 5-methyl derivative react with copper(II), nickel(II) and palladium(II) forming insoluble complexes. Their colour and incipient pH are given in the Table 1.

TABLE 1

Name of complex	Colour	Incipient-pH
1. Copper-ortho-hydroxy acetophenone oxime	Brownish	2.1—8.0
2. Nickel-ortho-hydroxy acetophenone oxime	Green	5.0—9.0
3. Palladium-ortho-hydroxy acetophenone oxime	Yellowish	1.0—4.5
4. Copper-2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone oxime	Dirty white	1.5—8.0
5. Nickel-2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone oxime	Light green	4.5—9.0
6. Palladium-2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone oxime	Yellow	1.0—5.0

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The composition of these complexes has been determined by carrying out conductometric and amperometric titrations of the metal solutions against the ligand.

Conductometric titrations : The conductometric titration of copper sulphate against ortho-hydroxy-acetophenone oxime as titrant indicates that the mole ratio in which copper and the ligand combine, is 1 : 2. Similar results are obtained in all the systems.

Amperometric titrations : The amperometric titrations of copper sulphate and palladium chloride were carried out, using a sodium-acetate-acetic acid buffer of pH 4.6 as supporting electrolyte, at a potential of -0.15 and -0.4 V. vs. S.C.E. respectively. Nickel sulphate was titrated at -1.2 V vs. S.C.E. and ammonia-ammonium chloride buffer (pH 9.0) being used as supporting electrolyte. A 0.01% gelatin solution was used as maximum suppressor.

The results of these titrations also prove the existence of 1 : 2 complex in all the systems.

Chemical analysis of the complexes : The pure dry samples of these complexes were analysed for the determination of their metal and nitrogen contents. The relevant analytical data are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2

Name of the complex	%Nitrogen		%Metal	
	Found	Calc.	Found	Calc.
1. bis (<i>o</i> -hydroxy acetophenone oxime) Cu(II)	7.4	7.71	17.7	17.35
2. bis (<i>o</i> -hydroxy acetophenone oxime) Ni(II)	7.5	7.80	16.00	16.36
3. bis (<i>o</i> -hydroxy acetophenone oxime) Pd(II)	7.2	6.88	25.80	26.18
4. bis (2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone oxime) Cu(II)	7.0	7.15	16.52	16.22
5. bis (2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone oxime) Ni(II)	7.4	7.24	14.90	15.17
6. bis (2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone oxime) Pd(II)	6.6	6.44	25.10	24.50

The analytical results clearly indicate their molecular formula to be $(L)_2M$ where LH stands for the ligand and M for the metal respectively.

Structure of the complexes : The infra-red spectra of the ligands and their metal complexes were recorded. Their characteristic frequencies are given in the following Table 3.

The ligands show strong absorption band characteristic of a phenolic group. But no such band is observed in the metal complexes. The disappearance of this band in the complexes clearly points to the replacement of the phenolic hydrogen by the metal. The $-C=N$ frequency is also lowered in the complexes. The lowering in the $-C=N$ frequency leads to the inference that the metal is also coordinated to the nitrogen of the oxime group.

TABLE 3

Absorption frequencies of ligands and their metal complexes

Compound	-OH (Phenolic) (cm ⁻¹)	-C = N (cm ⁻¹)
<i>o</i> -Hydroxy acetophenone oxime	3350	1620
bis(<i>o</i> -hydroxy acetophenone oxime) Cu(II)	—	1560
bis(<i>o</i> -hydroxy acetophenone oxime) Pd(II)	—	1550
bis(<i>o</i> -hydroxy acetophenone oxime) Ni(II)	—	1540
2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone oxime	3340	1590
bis(2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone oxime) Cu(II)	—	1540
bis (2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone oxime) Pd(II)	—	1545
bis (2-hydroxy-5-methyl acetophenone oxime) Ni(II)	—	1535

In the complexes a band at 3260 cm⁻¹ is observed. This band is assigned to OH of the oxime group. This lower OH frequency is attributed to intramolecular hydrogen bonding OH...O in the complexes⁴⁻⁶.

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